

Referencing (Giacomelli, 2025)

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Abstract

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Keywords: citation, epistemic delegation, iterability, rhetoric of science, symbolic capital, performativity, reflexivity, STS, semiotics, conceptual art

§ I

(Kuhn, 1962).

(Bazerman, 1988); (Latour & Woolgar, 1979); (Knorr Cetina, 1981).

(Latour & Fabbri, 1977): (Latour, 1987).

§ II

(Peirce, 1931–1958).

(Gilbert & Mulkey, 1984); (Hyland, 1999).

(Merton, 1968) — (Bourdieu, 1975); (Bourdieu, 1984).

(Garfield, 1955): (Small, 1978).

§ III

(Foucault, 1969): (Barthes, 1967).

(Derrida, 1972) — (Derrida, 1972).

§ IV

(Wittgenstein, 1953); (Wittgenstein, 1921).

(Latour & Woolgar, 1979): (Bazerman, 1988); (Gross, 1990).

§ V

(Ashmore, 1989); (Mulkay, 1985); (Woolgar, 1988).

(Gilbert & Mulkay, 1984) — (Hicks & Potter, 1991).

(Mulkay, Ashmore & Pinch, 1989).

§ VI

(Mallarmé, 1897).

(Duchamp, 1917); (Magritte, 1929).

(Borges, 1939) — (Cage, 1952); (Rauschenberg, 1953).

(Kosuth, 1965); (Kosuth, 1969). (Art & Language, 1969); (Broodthaers, 1968).

(Perec, 1969); (On Kawara, 1966).

(Goldsmith, 2011); (Kinross, 1992).

(Borgdorff, 2006).

§ VII

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(Ashmore, 1989): (Kosuth, 1969); (Derrida, 1972).

(Giacomelli, 2025).

References

- Art & Language. (1969). *Art-Language: The Journal of Conceptual Art*, 1(1). Kynoch Press.
- Ashmore, M. (1989). *The Reflexive Thesis: Wrihting Sociology of Scientific Knowledge*. University of Chicago Press.
- Barthes, R. (1967). La mort de l'auteur. *Manteia*, 5, 12–17. [Repr. in *Image, Music, Text*, trans. S. Heath, Fontana, 1977, pp. 142–148.]
- Bazerman, C. (1988). *Shaping Written Knowledge: The Genre and Activity of the Experimental Article in Science*. University of Wisconsin Press.
- Borgdorff, H. (2006). *The Debate on Research in the Arts*. Bergen National Academy of the Arts.
- Borges, J. L. (1939). Pierre Menard, autor del Quijote. *Sur*, 56, 7–16.
- Bourdieu, P. (1975). The specificity of the scientific field and the social conditions of the progress of reason. *Social Science Information*, 14(6), 19–47.
- Bourdieu, P. (1984). *Homo Academicus*. Éditions de Minuit.
- Broodthaers, M. (1968). *Musée d'Art Moderne, Département des Aigles* [Installation]. Wide White Space Gallery, Antwerp.
- Cage, J. (1952). *4'33''* [Musical composition]. First performed by David Tudor, Woodstock, NY.
- Derrida, J. (1972). Signature événement contexte. In *Marges de la philosophie* (pp. 365–393). Éditions de Minuit.
- Duchamp, M. (1917). *Fountain* [Readymade]. [Lost; documented in *The Blind Man*, no. 2.]
- Foucault, M. (1969). Qu'est-ce qu'un auteur? *Bulletin de la Société française de philosophie*, 63(3), 73–104.
- Garfield, E. (1955). Citation indexes for science. *Science*, 122(3159), 108–111.
- Giacomelli, M. (2025). *Referencing (Giacomelli, 2025)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20615593>
- Gilbert, G. N., & Mulkay, M. (1984). *Opening Pandora's Box: A Sociological Analysis of Scientists' Discourse*. Cambridge University Press.
- Goldsmith, K. (2011). *Uncreative Writing: Managing Language in the Digital Age*. Columbia University Press.
- Gross, A. G. (1990). *The Rhetoric of Science*. Harvard University Press.
- Hicks, D., & Potter, J. (1991). Sociology of scientific knowledge: A reflexive citation analysis. *Social Studies of Science*, 21(3), 459–501.

- Hyland, K. (1999). Academic attribution: Citation and the construction of disciplinary knowledge. *Applied Linguistics*, 20(3), 341–367.
- Kinross, R. (1992). *Modern Typography: An Essay in Critical History*. Hyphen Press.
- Knorr Cetina, K. (1981). *The Manufacture of Knowledge: An Essay on the Constructivist and Contextual Nature of Science*. Pergamon Press.
- Kosuth, J. (1965). *One and Three Chairs* [Installation]. Museum of Modern Art, New York.
- Kosuth, J. (1969). Art after philosophy. *Studio International*, 178(915–917), 134–137, 160–161, 212–213.
- Kuhn, T. S. (1962). *The Structure of Scientific Revolutions*. University of Chicago Press.
- Latour, B. (1987). *Science in Action: How to Follow Scientists and Engineers Through Society*. Harvard University Press.
- Latour, B., & Fabbri, P. (1977). La rhétorique de la science. *Actes de la recherche en sciences sociales*, 13(1), 81–95.
- Latour, B., & Woolgar, S. (1979). *Laboratory Life: The Social Construction of Scientific Facts*. Sage.
- Magritte, R. (1929). *La trahison des images* [Oil on canvas]. Los Angeles County Museum of Art.
- Mallarmé, S. (1897). Un coup de dés jamais n'abolira le hasard. *Cosmopolis*, May 1897. [Book ed.: Gallimard, 1914.]
- Merton, R. K. (1968). The Matthew effect in science. *Science*, 159(3810), 56–63.
- Mulkay, M. (1985). *The Word and the World: Explorations in the Form of Sociological Analysis*. George Allen & Unwin.
- Mulkay, M., Ashmore, M., & Pinch, T. (1989). *Health and Efficiency: A Sociology of Health Economics*. Open University Press.
- On Kawara. (1966–2013). *Today series* [Paintings]. Various collections.
- Peirce, C. S. (1931–1958). *Collected Papers of Charles Sanders Peirce* (Vols. 1–8, C. Hartshorne, P. Weiss, & A. Burks, Eds.). Harvard University Press.
- Perec, G. (1969). *La Disparition*. Denoël.
- Rauschenberg, R. (1953). *Erased de Kooning Drawing* [Traces of drawing, label, and golden frame on paper]. San Francisco Museum of Modern Art.
- Small, H. (1978). Cited documents as concept symbols. *Social Studies of Science*, 8(3), 327–340.
- Wittgenstein, L. (1921). *Tractatus Logico-Philosophicus* (C. K. Ogden, Trans.). Kegan Paul, Trench, Trubner.

Wittgenstein, L. (1953). *Philosophical Investigations* (G. E. M. Anscombe, Trans.). Basil Blackwell.

Woolgar, S. (Ed.). (1988). *Knowledge and Reflexivity: New Frontiers in the Sociology of Knowledge*. Sage.